

EXPLORING MISCONFIGURATION VULNERABILITIES USING LARGE LANGUAGE MODELS: AN ANALYSIS OF THE NATIONAL VULNERABILITY DATABASE

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: Modern software systems rely on numerous configuration options to adapt functionality and behavior. While this flexibility is essential, it increases complexity and makes misconfigurations more likely. Such misconfigurations can introduce vulnerabilities that pose significant security risks. Despite their relevance, empirical analyses of misconfiguration vulnerabilities remain limited.

Methods: We analyzed explicitly described misconfiguration vulnerabilities from the National Vulnerability Database. To support large-scale categorization, we evaluated 17 large language models and assessed their classification performance and agreement.

Results: The strongest models achieved high classification performance on both a manually labeled reference dataset and a larger full dataset. Using the most consistent classifications, we analyzed 2,497 misconfiguration vulnerabilities across four vulnerability types. The results show that insecure configurations dominate the dataset, followed by improper configuration, unprotected value, and weak default. Across types, vulnerabilities are commonly associated with network attack vectors, low attack complexity, and long lifetimes.

Conclusion: Our findings provide empirical insights into the characteristics of real-world misconfiguration vulnerabilities and indicate that large language models can support their large-scale analysis. However, validation procedures remain important due to differences in classification behavior across models.

1. INTRODUCTION

Today’s software is increasingly characterized by highly configurable, integrated software platforms. These platforms typically build on selectively enabling, disabling, or combining functionalities (i.e., features), resulting in a large number of system variants [7]. This trend can be observed across a variety of domains (e.g., business [55], healthcare [54]) and system types (e.g., operating systems [25], cloud environments [87]). Examples include the Linux kernel [41], governed by numerous configuration options controlling subsystems, drivers, and low-level functionality, or SAP enterprise-resource-planning systems, which provide extensive configurability particularly at the business-process level [97, 69]. While this configurability provides flexibility that helps in aligning functionality with stakeholder requirements, it fundamentally changes software engineering itself. Instead of developing single, static products, software engineers must consider extensive configuration spaces (i.e., the set of all possible valid configurations [75]) where a system’s actual behavior is determined by specific configuration choices. Thus, configurability significantly increases system complexity, defined by the number of features and their configuration options [7, 71].

Parallel to this growth in system complexity, security threats and attacks have increased substantially in recent years [44, 101, 28]. For example, software bugs [100] or programming mistakes [27] become more likely, increasing the number of exploitable vulnerabilities and thus opportunities for real-world attacks [44]. In this context, the flexibility that makes configurable systems beneficial can also increase security threats even more [52, 51]. Specifically, configurability directly affects a system’s attack surface, as configuration options may unintentionally introduce additional attack vectors [60, 88] through which

malicious actors can interact with the system [49]. Such threats may arise both from invalid configurations (i.e., violation of syntactic or semantic constraints) [94, 93], as well as from valid configurations that nevertheless may result in unintended or vulnerable behavior, commonly referred to as misconfigurations [82, 5, 50]. In this context, we refer to vulnerabilities that are caused by configuration decisions as *misconfiguration vulnerabilities*.

In recent years, research interest in misconfiguration vulnerabilities has increased substantially. Accordingly, such vulnerabilities have been studied in a variety of contexts, for example, Internet-of-Things devices [81] or cloud environments [57]. In addition, several comprehensive literature studies have systematically synthesized existing knowledge to establish a broader understanding of misconfigurations and their security implications [50, 24]. This growing relevance is also reflected beyond academia. In its most recent edition of the *Top 10 security risk ranking*, released in November 2025, the Open Worldwide Application Security Project (OWASP) ranked misconfiguration vulnerabilities as the second most critical risk.¹

Problem Statement. Despite this relevance, systematic empirical knowledge about misconfiguration vulnerabilities in large vulnerability databases remains limited. The National Vulnerability Database (NVD) [15] provides textual vulnerability descriptions and metadata such as CWE mappings and CVSS scores, but configuration-specific information is not represented as a dedicated data field. As a result, identifying and categorizing misconfiguration vulnerabilities requires interpretation of heterogeneous natural-language descriptions [6]. Recent advances in Large Language Models (LLMs) provide a possible way to support this interpretation task at scale. Prior work has already used LLMs for security-related tasks, including vulnerability detection, classification, and repair [30] and the distinction between patches and exploits [61]. However, it remains unclear how reliably LLMs can support the identification and categorization of explicitly described misconfiguration vulnerabilities in NVD data and what such vulnerabilities reveal about severity, exploitability, affected security goals, and recurring configuration patterns.

To address this gap, we present the first systematic, large-scale LLM-based classification of explicitly described misconfiguration vulnerabilities in the NVD. Specifically, we first assess the classification reliability of 13 open-source and four closed-source LLMs on a manually labeled ground truth dataset. We then use the best-performing models to analyze a larger set of 4,231 candidate CVE entries extracted from the NVD. Our results show that misconfiguration vulnerabilities are dominated by insecure configurations, are overwhelmingly network-exploitable at low complexity, and persist for years at high severity.

Contributions. Overall, this paper makes the following contributions:

- A reproducible LLM-supported classification pipeline for identifying and categorizing explicitly described misconfiguration vulnerabilities in the NVD.
- An empirical characterization of 2,497 misconfiguration vulnerabilities with respect to vulnerability type, CWE associations, lifetime, exploitability, severity, and affected security goals.
- A curated dataset, prompts, model outputs, and analysis scripts to support transparency and independent follow-up studies.²

We aim to support both researchers and practitioners in better understanding how configuration decisions are reflected in vulnerability data. For researchers, our results provide empirical insights into the characteristics and prevalence of explicitly described misconfiguration vulnerabilities and offer a reusable dataset for follow-up studies. For practitioners, our findings provide a structured view of recurring vulnerability patterns that can inform secure defaults, configuration reviews, deployment checks, and vulnerability management.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 introduces the terminology needed for the study. Section 3 describes the selected open-source and closed-source LLMs. Section 4 presents the study design, dataset construction, classification scheme, prompting strategy, and evaluation procedure.

¹www.owasp.org/Top10/2025

²www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18908683

Section 5 reports the classification reliability assessment. Section 6 characterizes the resulting misconfiguration vulnerabilities. Section 7 discusses threats to validity, Section 8 summarizes related work, and Section 9 concludes the paper.

2. BACKGROUND

In the following, we provide key information on (mis)configuring, vulnerabilities, and LLMs.

2.1. (Mis)Configuring. Software systems typically rely on configuring to adapt functionality and behavior to customer demands, industry standards, or legal regulations through selecting (i.e., enabling, disabling) and combining features [1, 7]. System configuring is typically realized using variability mechanisms at the implementation level (e.g., preprocessor directives [47], dependency injection [73]). While configurability offers higher customer satisfaction, it also introduces significant challenges due to the vast size of modern configuration spaces, leading to an exploding amount of feature combinations [75]. Configurations can be classified as *invalid* or *valid*. An invalid configuration refers to a configuration that a system cannot support or interpret according to its specification, often failing to satisfy feature constraints or allowable configurations defined at implementation level [72, 11]. In contrast, valid configurations satisfy all constraints (e.g., defined by a variability model), but are still unsuitable for the intended context [58]. Such cases are referred to as *misconfigurations* [71, 53], which are particularly critical with respect to security [18, 23], for example, in the context of insufficient security hardening [34]. Thus, misconfigurations can lead to vulnerabilities that potentially allow exploitation due to their violation of the security goals confidentiality, integrity, and/or availability [52, 2, 85].

2.2. Security Vulnerabilities. Security vulnerabilities are weaknesses that constitute the technical precondition for security incidents and must be distinguished from threats and risks. Threats describe events with a potential negative impact on a system, for example, unauthorized access [62, 36]. A vulnerability becomes security-relevant when it can be leveraged by such a threat. The resulting risk is determined by the exploitation likelihood and the severity of consequences [36]. Vulnerabilities are often documented in vulnerability databases (e.g., NVD [15]), containing descriptions and system- or vulnerability-related metadata, standardized identifiers, classifications, and severity-assessment schemes [39, 12]. The Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVEs) system provides identifiers for reported vulnerabilities, while, at a higher level of abstraction, the Common Weakness Enumerations (CWEs) describe recurring types that underlie concrete vulnerability instances [12]. To rate severity, the Common Vulnerability Scoring System (CVSS) is used, assigning scores on a scale from 0.0 (no severity) to 10.0 (critical severity) [59]. Over time, CVSS has evolved into multiple versions (e.g., v3.1) that refine how vulnerability severity is assessed. Depending on the version, scores are computed using different metrics capturing exploitability, impact, and contextual factors [4].³

2.3. Large-Language Models. LLMs are deep-learning architectures, predominantly based on the transformer architecture [89], designed to process and generate human-like text. Their architecture allows for efficient parallelization over multiple graphics-processing units during training and inference, resulting in large LLMs and enhanced sample efficiency across a broad range of downstream tasks [91]. Unlike traditional machine-learning algorithms that rely on manual feature engineering, LLMs are trained on huge datasets with trillions of tokens, over multiple training stages (i.e., unsupervised pre-training [67], supervised fine-tuning [67, 64], or reinforcement learning [74, 42]), allowing them to excel in classical natural-language-processing (NLP) tasks [66], but also to apply step-by-step reasoning [92] to solve complex tasks. Specifically, the supervised fine-tuning-training stage (primarily used for teaching instruction following) enables *few-shot* learning (also referred to as in-context learning) [19], the ability to complete a task given a small number of examples, allowing the LLM to perform tasks it was not explicitly trained for via natural-language prompting [45]. Few-shot learning is an important ability for classification tasks, as it allows the use of LLMs from the shelf, without having to train (i.e., to fine-tune) them on a specific classification task. More recent architectural developments led to a focus on LLMs with a Mixture-of-Experts (MoE) architecture [37], where the number of active parameters is reduced during inference by training a routing algorithm, which is tasked with selecting the best subsections (i.e., experts) of an LLM to answer a prompt, thus significantly reducing both the inference latency and cost.

³nvd.nist.gov/vuln-metrics/cvss

In recent years, LLMs have been extensively trained and/or used for tasks in software and security engineering, including code translation [70], code generation [9, 33], vulnerability detection [30], or code repair [29].

3. MODELS

In this work, we aim to evaluate the performance of both open-source and (proprietary) closed-source LLMs and later use the best-performing and most reliable models for vulnerability classification. In total, we initially rely on three open-source LLM families (i.e., 13 LLMs) and four closed-source LLMs, which are described in the following. Note that, in contrast to open-source LLMs, closed-source LLMs typically provide only limited architectural details. Consequently, our descriptions of these models are less detailed.

3.1. Open-Source LLMs. Open-source LLMs have been an integral part of the rapid succession of LLM versions in recent years. Particularly, the research labs at Meta [86], Alibaba [10], and Google [84] have made crucial contributions, releasing new LLM versions almost every few months. In this work, we focus on the most recent generations of LLM families from Alibaba (Qwen3) and Google (Gemma-3), as well as the most recent open-source contribution from OpenAI (gpt-oss). They offer LLMs spanning multiple parameter scales, enabling a comprehensive analysis over different LLM sizes.

Qwen3 [96], released in April 2025, is a family of nine multilingual LLMs, comprising six dense and three MoE LLMs.⁴ For our study, we focus on seven LLMs (six dense and one MoE): Qwen3-0.6B, Qwen3-1.7B, Qwen3-4B, Qwen3-8B, Qwen3-14B, Qwen3-32B, and Qwen3-Next-80B-A3B. For all seven selected LLMs, the *instruct* version is used. These versions are also trained to apply *reasoning*, but only do so to a limited extent. The one MoE LLM, Qwen3-Next-80B-A3B, activates three billion of its 80 billion parameters during inference.

Gemma-3, released in March 2025, is a multimodal (with a vision encoder for image inputs) and multilingual LLM family, consisting of four dense LLMs: Gemma-3-1b, Gemma-3-4b, Gemma-3-12b, and Gemma-3-27b. For all four selected LLMs, the *instruct* version is used. Furthermore, all four LLMs are not trained to apply a step-by-step reasoning approach before generating the final answer.

gpt-oss-120b and gpt-oss-20b are two open-source reasoning LLMs from OpenAI with a MoE architecture [63], both released in August 2025. Both LLMs use the same architecture, number of layers, query-, and key-/value-heads. They differ only in the number of experts per layer. The larger 120b version uses 128 experts, and the smaller 20b version uses 32. Both LLMs use four experts per layer during inference.

3.2. Closed-Source LLMs. While most frontier AI labs publish some open-source LLMs, most don't publish their strongest models openly, but only make them available as closed-source (proprietary) LLMs that can be accessed through an API. In this work, we use the following four closed-source LLMs from four different vendors, which we access through their respective API:

- **ChatGPT 5.2**⁵ by OpenAI.
- **DeepSeek V3.2** [26] (also referred to as DeepSeek Reasoner) by DeepSeek.
- **Gemini 2.5 Pro**⁶ by Google.
- **Claude Sonnet 4.5**⁷ by Anthropic.

The four closed-source LLMs represented the most recent contribution for each vendor available through their respective API as of the time of the study. Here, DeepSeek V3.2 is not a fully closed-source LLM, as it is available via HuggingFace; we use it through DeepSeek's proprietary API with reasoning enabled. Thus, we count it as a closed-source LLM in the context of this study.

⁴including one MoE, released later: qwen.ai/blog?id=4074cca80393150c248e508aa62983f9cb7d27cd

⁵openai.com/index/introducing-gpt-5-2

⁶ai.google.dev/gemini-api/docs/models/gemini-2.5-pro

⁷www.anthropic.com/news/claude-sonnet-4-5

FIGURE 1. Overview of the study method, including the number of CVE entries and research question assignments.

4. METHOD

This section describes the study method used to construct, classify, validate, and analyze the NVD-based dataset. We first define the study goal and research questions, then describe the dataset construction, classification scheme, prompting strategy, reference labeling, model-based classification, and final vulnerability characterization.

4.1. Goal and Research Questions. The major goal of this paper is to characterize explicitly described misconfiguration vulnerabilities in NVD data and to assess whether LLMs can support the required classification task with sufficient reliability. To achieve this goal, we define the following RQs:

RQ₁ 🗑️ **How reliably can LLMs support the classification of explicitly described misconfiguration vulnerabilities?** We assess whether LLMs can assign CVE entries to four predefined misconfiguration vulnerability types based on textual CVE descriptions and CWE information. For this purpose, we evaluate all models on a manually labeled reference dataset and analyze model agreement on the larger full dataset. This RQ focuses on classification reliability rather than establishing an independent ground truth for the entire dataset.

RQ₂ 🔍 **How are misconfiguration vulnerabilities characterized in NVD metadata?** We classify misconfiguration vulnerabilities based on CVE descriptions and CWE categories, as well as to analyze the vulnerability types with respect to their risk characteristics using NVD metadata (e.g., CVSS). By examining the distribution of severity metrics across types, we provide insights into recurring properties of misconfigurations and their security implications. This RQ focuses on empirical characteristics observable in NVD metadata rather than on reconstructing the root causes of individual vulnerabilities.

By addressing the RQs, we aim to provide empirical insights into the applicability of LLMs for analyzing security data, specifically misconfiguration vulnerabilities documented as CVEs, and to derive characterizations of such vulnerabilities.

4.2. Study Design. We follow a nine-step study design, as illustrated in Figure 1. The study design follows established recommendations for mining datasets in software engineering [98] and complies with common data-quality criteria for data collection and analysis [16]. In the following, we describe the preparation steps of the study. Details on the study conduct are provided in Section 4.3.

Dataset. We rely on the NVD, which is a widely established, authoritative repository, providing comprehensive coverage of publicly disclosed vulnerabilities [95, 39]. Therefore, we consider it well-suited to serve as a basis for our study. Vulnerability entries can be retrieved using the NVD API 2.0.⁸ Since

⁸nvd.nist.gov/developers/vulnerabilities

the NVD entries are provided in JSON format, we applied a transformation step to extract relevant attributes and convert them into a relational structure. This mapping enables the representation of CVE information in rows and columns compatible with a relational database schema. The transformed data was stored in a local MySQL database, resulting in a structured and queryable dataset for subsequent analysis.

Entry Selection. To identify only relevant entries, we defined the following Inclusion Criteria (ICs):

IC₁ The vulnerability and its description contain explicit misconfiguration-related terms.

IC₂ The vulnerability status is either *modified* or *analyzed*.

IC₃ The vulnerability was published between 2010 and 2025.

By applying **IC₁**, we restrict the dataset to vulnerabilities conceptually aligned with misconfiguring. Note that we are aware that configuration aspects are often only implicitly described, as also indicated by their high prevalence in the OWASP Top 10 analysis. However, we deliberately focus on explicitly described cases, since we assume that LLMs require concrete and unambiguous descriptions to allow effective classifications. To select vulnerabilities, we applied an AND-OR-keyword logic, requiring the occurrence of `misconfig*` AND at least one term from a predefined list of 29 keywords (e.g., *insecure*, *improper*, *invalid*). By relying on **IC₂**, we ensure that only entries that have undergone a sufficient level of review are considered. Other status values (e.g., *deferred*, *received*) were intentionally excluded because they typically indicate preliminary, disputed, or incomplete CVEs. Finally, **IC₃** restricts the analysis to vulnerabilities that reflect contemporary software and security practices, while still covering a sufficiently long period to enable the identification of stable trends and developments over time.

Classification Scheme and Metadata. The classification scheme builds on concepts reported in prior literature and operationalizes them into four mutually exclusive *vulnerability types*. The types are intended to capture the primary configuration-related mechanism described in a CVE entry. If several mechanisms appear plausible, the prompt instructs the model to select the type most directly supported by the CVE description and CWE information.

Insecure configurations [27, 99, 46]: denote valid configurations in which security risks originate from the selected features or their interactions. The lack of security is intrinsic to the feature set and persists regardless of parameter settings, as secure operation is hardly achievable. Examples include the integration of components with known vulnerable functionality [79] or insecure control flows or authentication bypasses [56].

Improper configurations [46, 43, 21]: describe valid configurations where security-relevant parameters are incorrectly set or omitted. Although the selected features support secure operation, the required security controls are not properly enabled. Examples include improper TLS certificate configurations [13] or overly permissive container options such as Docker mounts [3].

Weak defaults [27, 46, 68]: refer to valid default configurations that remain unchanged and expose the system to security risks. Examples include default configurations of Internet-of-Things device software [77] or insecure DNS default settings [48].

Unprotected values [27, 99, 68]: refer to valid configurations in which sensitive values, such as credentials or tokens, are accessible or insufficiently protected. Security issues arise from the exposure of the value itself, rather than from the configuration of general protection mechanisms. Examples include exposed credentials, private keys, certificates, or insufficiently secured access tokens in configuration files, scripts, or deployment templates [17, 65].

To make the classification scheme operational, Table 1 shows each vulnerability type and illustrates it with a representative CVE from the manually labeled reference dataset.

To further characterize the entries, we rely on NVD metadata, including publication date, last modification date, CWE, CVSS base metrics (attack vector, attack complexity, privileges required, user interaction, scope, confidentiality impact, integrity impact, availability impact), and derived CVSS scores (base score, base severity, exploitability score, impact score). Note that we focus on CVSS v3.1.

Manual Reference Dataset. The manual reference dataset serves as an initial correctness reference for evaluating the LLM-based classification process. It was manually labeled by the first author before running the LLM evaluation. To cover all predefined vulnerability types equally, the dataset contains

TABLE 1. Examples for the four misconfiguration vulnerability types.

type	CVE	short description
insecure configuration	CVE-2017-12319	Only devices with a specific network feature enabled are vulnerable.
improper configuration	CVE-2021-30346	Improper configuration enables access to secure resources.
weak default	CVE-2019-2041	An insecure default value affects NFC module configuration.
unprotected value	CVE-2024-20490	HTTP proxy credentials are logged in clear text.

15 CVE entries per type, resulting in 60 entries overall. This balanced design supports per-type performance assessment, but it does not reflect the expected distribution of types in the NVD full dataset. The reference entries were excluded from the subsequent full dataset analysis to avoid evaluating and analyzing the same entries twice.

Evaluation Metrics. We use precision, recall, F1, and macro F1 to assess model performance on the manual reference dataset. Precision measures how many entries assigned to a type actually belong to that type, while recall measures how many entries of a type are retrieved by the model. F1 is the harmonic mean of precision and recall. Macro F1 is computed by first calculating F1 separately for each vulnerability type and then averaging over all types. This metric is appropriate for our balanced reference dataset and prevents performance on one type from dominating the overall score [?].

For the larger full dataset, no independent manual label is available. We therefore use a model agreement to assess classification consistency. Specifically, we compute Leave One Out (LOO) F1 scores and Krippendorff’s α for nominal labels. LOO F1 compares each model against a consensus label derived from the other models and therefore avoids using the evaluated model to construct its own reference [?]. Krippendorff’s α [?] measures inter-rater agreement among several raters beyond chance, with each LLM treated as one rater.

Model Prompting. For all model evaluations and the classifications, we employ a similar prompting setup based on a Python script. We argue that using the same prompt structure ensures methodological consistency and prevents performance differences from being attributed to prompt variations rather than to the capabilities of the models themselves.

The *system prompt* defines the overall classification task and provides explicit definitions for all vulnerability types. To support structured reasoning, it includes a step-by-step decision guide based on an if-then-else logic (cf. replication package). In the context of the full-dataset evaluation, this guide explicitly instructs the model to assign a non-configuration label if none of the predefined types apply, avoiding forced assignments and improving classification robustness. In addition, the system prompt specifies strict output requirements to ensure uniform and machine-readable results. To enable few-shot learning, it further contains three synthetic example CVE descriptions per type, each accompanied by the corresponding output and CWE reference. These examples are deliberately artificial and do not correspond to real CVE entries, preventing memorization effects or data leakage.

The *user prompt* contains only the instance-specific input, namely the vulnerability description to be classified together with its associated CWE information. This clear separation between system-level task specification and user-level input supports reproducibility and ensures identical conditions. In the following, the general scheme of the prompt used via Python is given:

```

PROMPTS["SYSTEM_PROMPT"] = """
## task description
You are a cyber security expert tasked with classifying CVE descriptions into one of the
following pre-defined categories.
## CVE categories
{categories}
## step-by-step guide
{if-then-else logic}
## examples with input and output
{example CVE description per category}
{output per category}
## output requirements
ONLY return the category as written in the description (i.e., lowercase and no punctuation
added).
"""

PROMPTS["USER_PROMPT"] = """
Please categorize the following CVE description.
Description: {CVE description, CWE}
Output:
"""

```

4.3. Conduct. The study was conducted according to the steps shown in Figure 1. First, the third author retrieved all vulnerability entries from the NVD on January 05, 2026, resulting in 326,054 CVE entries. The raw JSON data were transformed into a relational schema and stored in a local MySQL database (step 1). Second, we applied the entry selection criteria to derive the full dataset of explicitly described misconfiguration-related CVE entries (step 2). This filtering resulted in 4,291 candidate entries. From this full dataset, we constructed a balanced manual reference dataset with 15 entries per vulnerability type, resulting in 60 manually labeled entries (step 3). The remaining 4,231 entries formed the larger full dataset for model-based classification. Third, the first and second authors executed the classification pipeline for all 13 open source and four closed source LLMs on the manual reference dataset using the same prompt template and Python-based evaluation script (step 4). For each model, we computed per-type F1 scores and macro F1 over all four vulnerability types. Closed-source models and computationally efficient (i.e., MoE) open-source models with a macro F1 of at least 0.80 were retained for classification of the larger full dataset. Fourth, the retained models were applied to the remaining 4,231 candidate entries using the same prompt configuration (steps 5 and 6). For the larger full dataset, we assessed model consistency through LOO F1 and Krippendorff’s α rather than treating model consensus as independent ground truth (step 7). Based on these results, we retained the four closed-source LLMs for the final vulnerability characterization. Fifth, we derived the final analysis dataset through consensus filtering (step 8). Entries classified as non-configuration-related by at least two retained models were excluded. Entries for which fewer than three retained models agreed on the same vulnerability type were also excluded. This resulted in a final analysis dataset of 2,497 CVE entries. As a plausibility check, the first author manually inspected 100 randomly selected entries from the final analysis dataset. This check was used to identify obvious inconsistencies in the consensus-based labels, but it does not replace an independent manual validation of the complete dataset. Finally, the classified dataset was analyzed in Python by the first author and jointly interpreted by the first and fourth author, resolving disagreements through discussion until consensus was reached (step 9).

5. LLM CLASSIFICATION EVALUATION

To answer RQ₁, we assess whether LLM-based classification is sufficiently reliable to support the subsequent characterization of misconfiguration vulnerabilities. We first evaluate all 13 open source and four closed source LLMs on the manually labeled ground truth dataset. Then, we analyze classification consistency on the larger full dataset using LOO F1 scores and Krippendorff’s α . The goal of this

TABLE 2. F1 scores on reference dataset for each vulnerability type and full reference dataset, subdivided into open-source and closed-source LLMs. Best scores per subdivision are shown in bold, while the overall best scores are shown in italic (bold-italic if both apply).

LLM	Insec. Config.	Improper Config.	Weak Default	Unprot. Value	Full
Gemma-3-1b	0.00	0.41	0.00	0.00	0.10
Gemma-3-4b	0.63	0.75	0.50	0.75	0.66
Gemma-3-12b	0.67	0.70	0.72	0.93	0.75
Gemma-3-27b	0.77	0.78	0.77	0.97	0.82
Qwen3-0.6B	0.63	0.73	0.12	0.88	0.59
Qwen3-1.7B	0.75	0.84	0.69	0.79	0.77
Qwen3-4B	0.72	0.65	0.73	0.80	0.72
Qwen3-8B	0.80	0.72	0.84	0.85	0.80
Qwen3-14B	0.83	0.67	0.71	0.70	0.72
Qwen3-32B	0.83	0.93	0.81	0.85	0.85
Qwen3-Next-80B-A3B	0.79	0.88	0.76	0.89	0.83
gpt-oss-20b	0.77	0.81	0.72	0.80	0.78
gpt-oss-120b	0.90	0.87	0.85	0.80	0.85
ChatGPT 5.2	0.97	0.90	0.97	0.97	0.95
DeepSeek V3.2	0.93	0.79	0.90	0.93	0.89
Claude Sonnet 4.5	0.93	0.88	0.90	0.97	0.92
Gemini 2.5 Pro	0.90	0.90	0.94	0.93	0.92

section is to determine which models provide sufficiently consistent classifications for the following vulnerability analysis.

5.1. Reference-Dataset Evaluation. We report the results of the reference-dataset evaluation in Table 2. All four closed-source LLMs consistently outperformed the open-source LLMs across the full reference dataset. The two best-performing open-source LLMs `gpt-oss-120b` and `Qwen3-32B` reached an F1 score of 0.85 on the full reference dataset, with `Qwen3-Next-80B-A3B` being slightly weaker, with an F1 score of 0.83. `ChatGPT 5.2` was the strongest closed-source LLM with an F1 score of 0.95 (12% higher than the best open-source LLM). Furthermore, `ChatGPT 5.2` and `Gemini 2.5 Pro` were the only two LLMs that reached an F1 score of 0.90 or higher for each vulnerability type.

Open-source LLMs. The results for all three open-source families show that performance on the reference dataset increased with LLM size, with the smallest two LLMs, `Qwen3-0.6B` and `Gemma-3-1b`, underperforming. Especially, `Gemma-3-1b` underperformed significantly on the classification task, as it returned improper configuration for almost 58 of 60 examples, with the remaining two being classified as secure configuration, a class (or type) not defined as part of the classification task. The results in Table 2 show that all LLMs had at least one vulnerability type in which they were weaker compared to the other vulnerability types. The Gemma-3 LLMs (excluding `Gemma-3-1b`) were relatively strong on unprotected value, with `Gemma-3-27b` being the only LLM equaling the performance of `ChatGPT 5.2` (0.97), but relatively weak on insecure configuration and improper configuration. While the Gemma-3 LLMs showed a mostly linear increase in performance, both for each vulnerability type and over the full dataset, the performance of the Qwen3 LLMs was fluctuating. For instance, `Qwen3-1.7B` achieved an F1 score of 0.77 over the full dataset, while `Qwen3-4B` and `Qwen3-14B` only achieved 0.72. This fluctuation was driven primarily by the lower F1 score on improper configuration for both LLMs. `Qwen3-32B` was the strongest open-source LLM on improper configuration, with a score of 0.93, while being relatively robust on the remaining three vulnerability types, with no F1 score being lower than 0.80. `Qwen3-Next-80B-A3B` was second-best open-source LLM on improper configuration (0.88) and third-best open-source LLM on unprotected value (0.89), while being somewhat weaker on insecure configuration (0.79) and weak default (0.72). `gpt-oss-120b`, on the other hand, was weakest on unprotected value (0.80), and strongest open-source LLM on weak default (0.85) and insecure configuration (0.90), while being relatively strong on improper configuration (0.87) compared to the other open-source LLMs. On the other hand, the smaller

TABLE 3. LOO-F1 scores for each vulnerability type over the full dataset, subdivided into open-source and closed-source LLMs. Best scores are shown in bold.

LLM	Insec. Config.	Improper Config.	Weak Default	Unprot. Value	Full
gpt-oss-120b	0.38	0.43	0.55	0.36	0.43
Qwen3-Next-80B-A3B	0.28	0.39	0.53	0.36	0.39
ChatGPT 5.2	0.91	0.84	0.70	0.81	0.81
DeepSeek V3.2	0.92	0.66	0.76	0.82	0.79
Claude Sonnet 4.5	0.92	0.76	0.78	0.82	0.82
Gemini 2.5 Pro	0.97	0.91	0.90	0.90	0.92

gpt-oss-20b was relatively weak on insecure configuration (0.77), and its weakest was on improper configuration (0.72). These results show that the larger open-source LLMs were capable of classifying misconfiguration vulnerabilities based on NVD entries moderately well, with a few LLMs being able to classify one class very well, with an F1 score of 0.90 or higher, but no LLM did so consistently over all vulnerability types. For the evaluation on the full NVD dataset, we used gpt-oss-120b and Qwen3-Next-80B-A3B, as they were the strongest and third strongest on the full reference dataset, while also being very fast due to their MoE architecture. We did not select Qwen3-32B, as it is significantly slower than Qwen3-Next-80B-A3B due to its dense architecture.

Closed-source LLMs. Compared to the open-source LLMs, the closed-source LLMs were more robust across the vulnerability types. While only two open-source LLMs, gpt-oss-120b and Qwen3-32B, achieved an F1 score of 0.80 or higher on all vulnerability types, nearly all closed-source LLMs achieved an F1 score of 0.90 or higher across all vulnerability types. Only Claude Sonnet 4.5 (0.88) and DeepSeek V3.2 (0.79) were weaker on improper configuration. The latter was the largest outlier among the closed-source LLMs. Overall, improper configuration was the vulnerability type on which all closed-source LLMs were weakest, whereas unprotected value was the vulnerability type with the highest average F1 score across the four closed-source LLMs.

5.2. Full-Dataset Evaluation. We acknowledge that a limitation of our study is the size of the reference dataset ($n=60$), as well as the equal weighting of each class in the reference-dataset evaluation, since we did not know the true distribution of vulnerability types a priori. However, this size was deliberately chosen to better preserve the full dataset for classification and analysis in \equiv **RQ2**. To strengthen our evaluation results, we approximated the F1 scores on the full dataset by determining a pseudo ground truth, using a LOO approach [80]. For each closed-source LLM, a pseudo ground-truth label for a given CVE was established through majority consensus among the remaining three LLMs, such that if at least two of the three other LLMs agree on a vulnerability type, that vulnerability type was taken as the pseudo ground-truth label. Cases where no such consensus existed were excluded from evaluation. For each LLM, we calculated the per-class LOO-F1 and the macro-averaged LOO-F1 across all vulnerability classes. The resulting LOO-F1 scores per LLM quantify how consistently a LLM’s classifications align with peer consensus. Moreover, we computed Krippendorff’s α to study the inter-rater agreement across all six LLMs on the full NVD dataset, treating each LLM as a nominal rater. The LOO-F1 results on the full NVD dataset are shown in Table 3.

Closed-source LLMs. The LOO-F1 results on the pseudo ground truth largely confirmed the findings of the reference-dataset evaluation, while also revealing important nuances in cross-LLM consistency. Gemini 2.5 Pro achieved the highest macro-F1 of 0.92, consistent with its strong performance on the reference dataset, followed closely by Claude Sonnet 4.5 (0.82), ChatGPT 5.2 (0.81), and DeepSeek V3.2 (0.79). Similar to the reference-dataset evaluation, DeepSeek V3.2 shows a weakness on improper configuration (0.66). Overall, the results were largely consistent with the findings of the reference-dataset evaluation.

Open-source LLMs. The two open-source LLMs included in the LOO-F1 evaluation showed markedly different results. Both gpt-oss-120b (0.43) and Qwen3-Next-80B-A3B (0.39) showed substantially lower macro-F1 scores compared to their ground-truth performance of 0.85 and 0.83, respectively. Yet, this discrepancy does not indicate a deterioration in LLM quality, but underlines a systematic divergence

and the consensus established by the three closed-source LLMs. For the evaluation of the two open-source LLMs, we determined the pseudo ground-truth labels through majority consensus among the three best-performing LLMs of the reference-dataset evaluation: ChatGPT 5.2, Claude Sonnet 4.5, and Gemini 2.5 Pro.

Inter-rater agreement. The divergence in classification behavior was further supported by Krippendorff’s α of 0.40 computed across all six LLMs, which was significantly lower than for the four closed-source LLMs alone ($\alpha = 0.73$), suggesting that the open-source LLMs disagree with the consensus considerably. Therefore, we dropped the two open-source LLMs for the misconfiguration vulnerability analysis and focused only on the results of the closed-source LLMs.

5.3. **Findings.** Based on the evaluation results described above, we derive the following three findings.

Q Finding 1: Misconfiguration vulnerability types differ in their conceptual separability. The classification results indicate that the four vulnerability types are not equally easy to distinguish from CVE descriptions and CWE information. While *unprotected value* was consistently classified with high accuracy across most evaluated LLMs, *improper configuration* resulted in lower and more variable performance, even for the strongest models. This observation suggests that some vulnerability types are described more explicitly in NVD entries, whereas others overlap conceptually and linguistically. Consequently, not all misconfiguration vulnerability types appear equally well-suited for automated classification based solely on CVE descriptions and CWE information.

Q Finding 2: Performance on a reference dataset does not fully predict behavior on large-scale datasets. The rankings of the evaluated LLMs differed between the reference-dataset and full-dataset evaluations. While ChatGPT 5.2 achieved the strongest performance on the manually labeled reference dataset (F1=0.95), Gemini 2.5 Pro achieved the highest agreement on the full dataset (F1=0.92). This discrepancy indicates that strong performance on a relatively small manually labeled dataset does not necessarily translate into identical classification behavior on a substantially larger dataset. Thus, evaluations based solely on manually labeled benchmark datasets may provide an incomplete picture of how LLMs behave in large-scale vulnerability analyses.

Q Finding 3: Multi-model validation reduces model-specific classification bias. The full-dataset evaluation showed substantial differences in classification behavior between individual LLMs. This became particularly visible through the lower agreement of the open-source LLMs with the closed-source LLMs and through the differences between the reference-dataset and full-dataset evaluations. These observations indicate that automated vulnerability classifications can vary depending on the selected LLM and its underlying classification strategy. Consequently, relying on a single LLM introduces the risk of model-specific classification bias. Multi-model validation approaches, such as agreement-based evaluation and consensus-based filtering, therefore appear important when constructing large-scale vulnerability datasets using LLMs.

🏠, RQ₁: LLM Evaluation

The evaluated LLMs achieved varying levels of performance in classifying misconfiguration vulnerabilities from CVE descriptions and CWE information. While the strongest LLMs achieved high classification performance, the results also showed differences in classification difficulty between vulnerability types, differences in behavior between reference-dataset and full-dataset evaluations, and model-specific classification strategies. Overall, the results indicate that LLMs can support large-scale analyses of explicitly described misconfiguration vulnerabilities, but that agreement-based validation procedures remain important to reduce model-specific classification bias.

6. ≡ VULNERABILITY ANALYSIS

To only consider reliable classifications, we restricted the analysis to LLMs demonstrating sufficient performance and inter-rater reliability. Thus, only the classifications of the four closed-source LLMs were retained, i.e., ChatGPT 5.2, DeepSeek V3.2, Claude Sonnet 4.5, and Gemini 2.5 Pro, while the two open-source models were excluded (cf. Section 5.2). Moreover, we reduced the full dataset to CVEs with the most reliable classifications (i.e., 2,497 CVEs). The exclusion requirements are given in

FIGURE 2. Distribution of vulnerability lifetime (years) in relation to the CVSS base score (both rounded to integers) based on violin plots (i.e., density of lifetime), box-plots (i.e., median, interquartile range), and jittered scatters (i.e., raw observations).

Section 4.3. In the following, we first present the results and subsequently derive findings to address **RQ₂**.

6.1. Results. The results are structured according to the following three subtopics. Minor deviations from 100% may occur due to rounding effects. Note that some analyzed properties are originally mapped to specific values (i.e., weights) that contribute to the calculation of the CVSS base score (e.g., integrity impact). Fortunately, these values are consistently associated with classes (e.g., low, high),⁹ which we refer to in our analysis.

Types and Lifetime. As shown beyond other information in Figure 3, insecure configuration accounts for 1,303 vulnerabilities (52%), improper configuration includes 510 vulnerabilities (20%), unprotected value covers 409 vulnerabilities (16%), and weak default comprises 275 vulnerabilities (11%). Overall, 2228 vulnerabilities (89%) have an assigned CWE identifier. However, these are quite diverse. The most frequent CWE are CWE-862 (119, 5%), CWE-79 (113, 5%), CWE-20 (79, 3%), and CWE-306 (71, 3%). Regarding the types, improper configuration is mainly associated with CWE-862 (62, 12%), insecure configuration shows the highest share of missing CWE assignments (169, 13%), unprotected value is primarily linked to CWE-798 (27, 7%) and CWE-200 (21, 5%), and weak default reports missing CWE assignments for 31 vulnerabilities (11%).

We defined the lifetime of a vulnerability as the time span between its publishing date and the last modification date. Referring to all types (cf. Figure 2), the median lifetime is 2.2 years, with observed values ranging from less than 0.1 years to 7.6 years. At type level, improper-configuration vulnerabilities show a median lifetime of 1.4 years. Insecure-configuration vulnerabilities have a median lifetime of 2.5 years, while unprotected-value vulnerabilities show a median lifetime of 2.1 years. Weak-default vulnerabilities exhibit a median lifetime of 2.3 years. In the context of all types, the minimum observed lifetime is close to zero years, while maximum lifetimes range between 6.4 (weak default) and 7.6 years (improper configuration).

Attack Vectors and Exploitability. In all types, most misconfiguration vulnerabilities are exploitable via the network attack vector (1,801, 72%). It is followed by local attacks with 545 vulnerabilities (22%), adjacent network attacks with 123 vulnerabilities (5%), and physical attacks with 28 vulnerabilities (1%). This trend is similar at type level, where network attack vectors dominate, ranging from 69% (insecure configuration) to 84% (weak default). Attack complexity is predominantly rated as low. Across all types, 2,323 vulnerabilities (93%) exhibit low attack complexity, while 174 vulnerabilities (7%) are

⁹www.first.org/cvss/v3.1/specification-document

FIGURE 3. Distribution of CVEs per misconfiguration type for security goals and privileges required.

rated as high complexity. This distribution is consistent for all types, with low attack complexity ranging between 88% (weak default) and 94% (insecure configuration).

Regarding required privileges (cf. Figure 3), 1,346 vulnerabilities (54%) can be exploited without any privileges, 979 vulnerabilities (39%) require low privileges, and 172 vulnerabilities (7%) require high privileges. At type level, vulnerabilities requiring no privileges range from 46% for improper configuration to 61% for weak-default vulnerabilities, while all types otherwise follow the same pattern. User interaction is not required for 2,197 vulnerabilities (88%) and the scope is classified unchanged for 2,180 vulnerabilities (87%), both criteria with no notable type-specific deviations. The median exploitability score is 2.8 for the full dataset and for each type. Exploitability scores range from 0.5 to 3.9 (i.e., highest possible score) overall, with type-specific minima of 0.7 (improper configuration), 0.5 (insecure configuration), 0.5 (unprotected value), and 0.8 (weak default), while the maximum is 3.9 in all types.

Severity and Impact. The median CVSS base score for all misconfiguration vulnerabilities is 7.5, with observed values ranging from 2.4 to 10.0 (cf. Figure 2). Regarding the types, the median CVSS base score is nearly identical at 7.5 for all types. With respect to base severity, 1,042 vulnerabilities (42%) are rated as medium, 1015 vulnerabilities (41%) as high, 409 vulnerabilities (16%) as critical, and 31 vulnerabilities (1%) as low. The median impact score for all types is 3.6, with values ranging from 1.4 to 6.0. At type level, median impact scores amount to 4.1 for improper configuration, 3.6 for insecure configuration, 3.6 for unprotected value, and 4.2 for weak default.

Regarding confidentiality impact, high impact is reported for 1,431 vulnerabilities (57%), while 675 vulnerabilities (27%) show no confidentiality impact. For integrity impact, high impact accounts for 1,204 vulnerabilities (48%), and no impact for 933 vulnerabilities (37%). Availability impact is rated as high for 1,349 vulnerabilities (54%), with no impact reported for 1,072 vulnerabilities (43%). Referring

to the types, unprotected value shows different impacts compared to the other types. There is a higher share of high confidentiality impact with 305 vulnerabilities (75%), compared to values between 52% (insecure configuration) and 60% (weak default) in the remaining types. For integrity impact, unprotected value also exhibits the highest share of cases with no impact, accounting for 219 vulnerabilities (54%), while the other types range between 31% (weak default) and 36% (insecure configuration). With respect to availability impact, unprotected value shows a lower share of high impact cases with 139 vulnerabilities (34%), compared to values between 55% (weak default) and 63% (improper configuration) in the other types. An overview of the CIA impacts is given in Figure 3.

6.2. **Findings.** Relying on the analysis results, we derive the following three findings:

Q Finding 4: Misconfiguration vulnerabilities exhibit low-effort exploitability. Most vulnerabilities in the dataset are exploitable via remote network attack vectors, a pattern also widely reported in literature [8, 52, 51]. Furthermore, exploitation typically involves low attack complexity, requires little or no privileges, and rarely depends on user interaction. Therefore, unsurprisingly, exploitability scores are generally high across all misconfiguration types. Taken together, these conditions may indicate that many misconfiguration vulnerabilities arise in situations in which services or resources become reachable before or independently of authentication or explicit user interaction. While this pattern appears consistently across the analyzed types, the underlying causes differ, such as in the context of exposed network accessible services with missing or insufficient access restrictions (e.g., CVE-2020-11967). Overall, the observed attack conditions may suggest that misconfigurations frequently create system states that facilitate direct attacker interaction with vulnerable components. We argue that this observation highlights the importance of preventive security engineering approaches for configurable software systems [14].

Q Finding 5: Misconfiguration vulnerabilities affect security goals with type-specific impact patterns. The analyzed vulnerabilities frequently affect core security goals and often reach medium to critical severity levels. However, impact distributions differ across misconfiguration types. Unprotected-value vulnerabilities predominantly affect confidentiality because they expose sensitive data once accessible. In contrast, insecure configuration, improper configuration, and weak-default vulnerabilities show more balanced impact distributions, as insecure system states or operational settings may affect multiple security goals simultaneously. At the same time, a substantial share of vulnerabilities shows no direct impact on individual security goals. This finding may suggest that many misconfiguration vulnerabilities only create exposure conditions rather than directly violating confidentiality, integrity, or availability [27, 38].

Q Finding 6: Misconfiguration vulnerabilities can persist over extended lifetimes. While vulnerability lifetimes cover a broad range, including long-lived vulnerabilities with lower severity, a notable observation is that many vulnerabilities still exhibit high severity despite long lifetimes. This observation may be explained by operational factors discussed in prior work. Configuration parameters are often controlled by system operators during deployment and operation rather than by vendors (e.g., in big data processing systems [35]). Thus, mitigation frequently requires changes to operational environments instead of applying a simple patch. Moreover, multiple configuration options may be technically valid (cf. Section 2), making it unclear which settings represent a secure configuration in a specific deployment context, while configuration changes may affect a system itself or operational workflows. These challenges are amplified by the dependency of configurations on deployment environments, where a mitigation that resolves an issue in one setup may introduce new problems in another, for example, due to hidden (cross)dependencies [20, 52]. We argue that mitigation may often be delayed even after vulnerabilities are disclosed, leading organizations to temporarily accept the associated risks when mitigation effort, cost, or uncertainty is considered too high. This may suggest that the persistence of misconfiguration vulnerabilities is often driven less by technical limitations than by operational risk-management decisions [51], which, we believe, is particularly concerning given the increasing configurability of software systems.

≡ RQ₂: Misconfiguration Vulnerability Analysis

In the context of misconfiguration vulnerabilities, insecure-configuration vulnerabilities dominate, followed by improper configuration, unprotected value, and weak default. Across types, misconfiguration vulnerabilities frequently exhibit high but low-effort exploitability, substantial impact, and longer persistence in real-world systems.

7. THREATS TO VALIDITY

In the following, we detail threats to the internal, external, and construct validity related to our study.

7.1. Internal Validity. Internal validity is mainly affected by how misconfiguration vulnerabilities are identified and classified. Our approach relies on explicit configuration references in CVE descriptions, excluding implicitly described cases. To reduce ambiguity, we restricted the dataset to entries matching a strict keyword logic. Furthermore, manual construction of the reference dataset introduces subjectivity. We mitigated this by evaluating multiple independently trained models against the same reference data and applying uniform performance thresholds before full-dataset classification. Only models achieving an F1 score of at least 0.8 on the manually curated reference dataset were retained. To further assess classification reliability, model agreement was evaluated using Krippendorff’s α and additional F1 scores derived from a pseudo ground truth generated through a LOO strategy. Note that CVEs labeled as non-configuration-related do not imply absence of configuration relevance, but insufficient description clarity for robust automated classification. LLM-based classification further introduces risks related to stochastic behavior, prompt sensitivity, or model-specific biases. These risks were reduced by using a fixed prompt configuration, validating each model, and enforcing multi-model agreement by retaining only cases where at least three of four models produced the same classification. Another potential threat concerns training data leakage. As the training corpora of most LLMs are not publicly disclosed, it cannot be ruled out that parts of the NVD were included in the training data of some evaluated models.

7.2. External Validity. External validity is limited by reliance on the NVD as the sole data source. While authoritative, it does not cover vulnerabilities from other global or domain-specific databases (e.g., China National Vulnerability Database [32]). The final dataset size poses an additional limitation. Only CVEs with explicit and unambiguous descriptions were included, as preliminary experiments showed that vague or implicit descriptions prevent reliable classification. However, this approach improved reliability at the cost of coverage. In addition, due to the selection of our keywords, it is possible that we did not capture some relevant vulnerabilities that would have been explicit enough. The analysis is further restricted to vulnerabilities published between 2010 and 2025. Earlier vulnerabilities may be omitted, but, we argue, are less representative of current software systems and configuration practices. Overall, the results apply to explicitly described misconfiguration vulnerabilities, not to all vulnerabilities involving configuration issues.

7.3. Construct Validity. Construct validity is influenced by the operationalization of misconfiguration vulnerabilities into four types. This scheme was not intended as a complete taxonomy, but as a deliberately distinct and minimally overlapping abstraction, since overlapping types were found to undermine classification reliability. Empirically, the stability of this operationalization was assessed through inter-model agreement and pseudo reference-dataset evaluation. Of course, finer-grained or intersecting types may better reflect real-world complexity, such as proposed by Dietrich et al. [27], but would probably substantially reduce automated classification reliability. Accordingly, the categorization should be understood as pragmatic and task-specific. Additional threats stem from reliance on NVD metadata (e.g., CVSS scores, CWE), which may be incomplete or revised. We addressed this threat by combining multiple metadata attributes and focusing on relative patterns. Finally, reproducibility is constrained by the use of closed-source models. Due to their closed-source nature, the control over the models, their exact weights, and hyperparameters (e.g., temperature) is limited. Furthermore, the exact model behind an API and its hyperparameters may change over time. We partly addressed this issue by fixed prompt strategies, storing all model classifications, and enforcing cross-model agreement, enabling partial reproducibility at the input, output, and analysis levels.

8. RELATED WORK

There is a variety of related work addressing either analyses of NVD data or studies on misconfiguration vulnerabilities. Of course, there is a high amount of research related to *traditional* machine-learning algorithms for classifying NVD data, such as proposed by Siewruk et al. [76], who analyzed 41,000 CVEs with a hybrid text-mining approach combining latent Dirichlet allocation and support vector machines (F1 score >0.9). Related to LLM-based analyses, unsurprisingly, there are fewer studies, arguably due to the novelty of LLMs. ChatNVD by Chopra et al. [22] integrated the closed-source models ChatGPT 4o mini, Llama 3, and Gemini 1.5 Pro into a retrieval-augmented pipeline over the full NVD dataset to answer structured CVE queries. On a dataset with more than 66,000 CVEs, Talibzade et al. [83] compared embedding-based classifiers and direct prompting with several LLMs, including both closed-source (e.g., ChatGPT 4.1 nano) and open-source models (e.g., Qwen2.5), for CWE and severity prediction. Interestingly, they state that these LLMs do not outperform quite traditional Term-Frequency-Inverse-Document-Frequency embeddings in terms of capturing relevant CVE contexts. Furthermore, Ghosh et al. [31] relied on the open-source model MPT-7B, pre-trained, among others, on roughly 248,000 CVEs, and evaluated with F1 scores frequently >0.8 for structured vulnerability-classification tasks.

Despite their scale and methodological diversity, these studies did not focus on misconfiguration vulnerabilities as a systematically defined target class. However, research that focused more on misconfiguration vulnerabilities adopted different methodological approaches. An extensive trend analysis covering more than 145,000 CVEs was conducted by Singla et al. [78], yet misconfiguration vulnerabilities were implicitly included but not separated as a dedicated type. Web-misconfiguration vulnerabilities in the NVD were examined by Wainakh et al. [90], however, identifying only 55 explicitly labeled cases. Similarly, the study of 243 timing-side-channel vulnerabilities by Kholoosi et al. [40] included misconfigurations implicitly and without systematic classification.

In contrast to the related work described, our research explicitly focused on misconfiguration vulnerabilities from the NVD and additionally performed a systematic classification using both open-source and closed-source LLMs. Beyond applying LLMs, we did a performance evaluation of the reference dataset and full dataset tailored to misconfiguration-specific types. In this way, we argue, that our work is of great value for both researchers and practitioners in the context of vulnerability classification with a focus on the strongly evolving topic of misconfiguring and its security implications.

9. CONCLUSION

In this study, we investigated the potential of LLMs to analyze misconfiguration vulnerabilities from the NVD and derived six relevant findings. We showed that closed-source models, namely ChatGPT 5.2, DeepSeek V3.2, Claude Sonnet 4.5, and Gemini 2.5 Pro, achieved high classification performance on both the reference dataset (≈ 0.90 macro F1; $n=60$) and the full dataset (≈ 0.80 macro F1; $n=4,231$). In contrast, open-source models struggled to achieve consistently strong performance across datasets and vulnerability types. The analysis of the most consistently classified misconfiguration vulnerabilities ($n=2,497$) showed that insecure-configuration vulnerabilities dominate, followed by improper configuration, unprotected value, and weak default. Across all types, these vulnerabilities are commonly characterized by network-based attack vectors, low attack complexity, long lifetimes, and potentially severe security impacts.

We argue that our findings contribute to a better understanding of real-world misconfiguration vulnerabilities while demonstrating the potential of LLM-supported vulnerability analysis. For practitioners, they highlight recurring vulnerability characteristics that can support risk assessment and strengthen configuration awareness. For researchers, they provide an empirical foundation for studying misconfiguration vulnerabilities and developing automated approaches for configuration-aware security engineering. However, the results should be interpreted with caution, as the analysis is limited to explicitly described misconfiguration vulnerabilities, while implicitly described cases remain difficult to identify automatically. Future research should investigate whether alternative or more fine-grained classification schemes are needed and how implicitly described misconfiguration vulnerabilities can be identified more effectively. While this study relied on structured logical instructions to guide the models, future work could explore alternative reasoning approaches and domain-specific adaptation strategies to improve the classification of configuration-related security issues.

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